

IMPACT CHARACTERISTICS OF COMPOSITE LAMINATED SANDWICH STRUCTURES

Chun-Gon Kim and Eui-Jin Jun

Composite Materials Lab.

Korea Institute of Machinery and Metals

P.O.Box 41, Changwon 641-600, KOREA

ABSTRACT

The damage resistance of composite laminated sandwich plate was evaluated through drop weight impact tests and the measurement of damage size. The sandwich plate is made of Graphite/epoxy faces and Nomex honeycomb core. The size and shape of delamination due to impact for each interply locations were measured by the deply technique to investigate the impact damage mechanism. In deply technique, Kapton film was inserted along the interply edges of the laminated faces and Barium Sulfide was used as the penetrant into the impact damage area.

Compared are the impact behavior of a laminate and the facesheet of a sandwich plate. The measurement of delaminations due to impact for each interply location shows that the largest delamination occurs at the farthest interply location from the impact side for a laminate but it shifts inward interply location for the laminated facesheet of a sandwich. The observed shape of interply delamination under impact shows very peculiar regularity that the major axis of delamination falls upon the fiber direction of the immediate lower ply and a center band is parallel to the fiber direction of the immediate upper ply.

KEYWORDS : Composite Laminated Sandwich, Drop Weight Impact Test, Damage Resistance, Deply Technique, Delamination due to Impact.

1. INTRODUCTION

Sandwich structures are attractive in the aerospace industry because of their high bending stiffness. A sandwich structure is constructed of facesheet and core by bonding them together through adhesives. Laminated composite materials have high specific stiffness and strength, but

they are weak in impact loading. For high speed impact loading, the composite plates will be perforated and major damage area will be localized in the impacted zone. However, for low speed impact, the damage area of composite plate will be spread over a larger region. For thin composite plates, the low speed impact loading is quite similar to the transverse static loading [1]. So the damage of thin plates is mainly attributed to bending stresses. A part of the applied impact energy is converted into elastic deformation and the remaining part of the impact energy is absorbed by the specimen and results in permanent deformation and damage in the specimen such as matrix cracking, delamination, fiber breakage, and fiber matrix debonding. In case of sandwich structures, there are additional damages in core such as core crushing and shear deformation.

It has been concluded from experiments that delamination is the major damage mode in thin composite plates subjected to low velocity impact. It is important to understand the relationship between impact energy and delamination area for the impact resistance of a composite structure. The impact delamination was reported to be two-lobed shapes using deply techniques[2]. An impact delamination model was proposed which explains the distribution of its preferential direction of two lobed shape[3]. Experimental results have suggested that the bending stiffness mismatching between adjacent plies is responsible for the delamination at the interply [4]. Impact resistance of sandwich panels was studied by several researchers [5-8]. Bernard and Lagace[7] evaluated the effects of low energy impact on the sandwich panels with various core materials and core thickness. The damage modes occurring in the facesheets, the cores, and facesheet-core interfaces were examined. The macroscopic failure modes, micro failure mechanisms, and energy absorbing characteristics of these composite sandwich panels were studied by using instrumented impact test and micrography in the Reference 8. In case of tough facesheets, the impact resistance of composite sandwich panels was found to be controlled by the facesheets and relatively independent of the density of foam core. The impact failure mechanism of sandwich panels containing less tough facesheet was found to change from facesheet dominated to foam core-dominated behavior.

In this research, the impact resistances of composite laminates and sandwich panels were compared through quantitative measurements of delamination and the instrumented impact test. The role of sandwich core under impact loading was studied by comparing the impact behavior of a lamiate and the facesheet of a sandwich.

2. EXPERIMENT

The composite laminates and sandwich panels were made of Graphite/epoxy prepreg and Nomex core. The prepreg was made by Hankook Fiber Glass Co, Korea. and has similar mechanical properties to AS/3501. Two variables of interest in these experiments are the layup sequences and core density. Two quasi-isotropic layup sequences are selected to show the shape and the extent of impact damages : $[0/45/90/-45]_s$ and $[45/-45/0/90]_s$. The first layup is abbreviated as Q1 and the second as Q2. Sandwich specimens were fabricated by bonding

facesheets of the above layups and Nomex honeycomb core through adhesive films. Two types of Nomex core were used, HRH-1/8-3pcf (abbreviated as H3) and HRH-1/8-8pcf (H8). The dimensions of a deplying specimen are shown in Figure 1 for the measurement of impact delamination by the deply technique. For the ease of deplying between layers after impact, Kapton film was inserted along the interply edges of the specimen. All the specimens were simply supported by a ring support of which the diameter is 50.8mm (2.0 in.) during the drop weight impact testing. Three impact energy levels were considered, 2.10 J, 3.78 J, and 5.03 J.

A 2.0 mm diameter hole was drilled at the center of impact dent of the specimen shown in Figure 1 just after the impact test. Then the specimens were soaked into the penetrant (Barium Sulfide, BaSO₄) and kept in the vacuum oven for 12 hours. The penetrant was selected because the solution easily penetrates into the delamination surface and makes a good contrast image after drying for a black specimen. The dried specimens were deplied at room temperature. Ply by ply delamination sizes were measured by this technique for laminates, Q1 and Q2, and sandwiches, Q1H3, Q1H8, Q2H3, and Q2H8, impacted at $E_0=2.10$ J, 3.78 J, and 5.03 J.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 2 shows the load history curves for composite laminate (Q1) and sandwich (Q1H3). The load history curve of the laminate shows a sudden drop after almost linear increase, which is the sign of considerable damage propagation. While that of the sandwich plate shows only a limited damage propagation. That interpretation is obvious in energy history curves shown in Figure 3. In an energy history curve, the maximum is equal to the applied impact energy to the specimen and the final value of the energy history curve is equal to the absorbed energy by an impacted specimen. That is to say, laminates absorb much more energy than sandwich plates, so it can be predicted that there will be much more impact damages in laminates than in sandwich plates.

The delamination due to impact can be measured using X-ray, C-scan, or Section microscopy, but these are not accurate ways of measuring it because it is a kind of 3-dimensional defect embedded in a composite laminate. To measure the delamination in each interply location quantitatively, a deply technique was adopted. Figure 4 shows the ply by ply delamination for a composite laminate (Q1) and a composite faced sandwich plate (Q1H3). The photographs were taken viewing the delamination from the opposite side of impacted face. The delamination due to low speed impact is largest in the farthest interply from the impact side. This is because the bending stress due to impact results in most severe matrix cracking in the farthest side. The matrix cracking gives rise to the delamination in the interply. A close look at the shape of ply by ply delamination shows that it is two-lobed shape and the major axis of delamination falls upon the fiber direction of the immediate lower ply and center strip is parallel to the fiber of the immediate upper ply in each interply location. These ply by ply photographs clearly show the validity of G. Clark's impact delamination model. G. Clark's delamination model is shown for the interply, [.45/0..] in Figure 5. Considering two adjacent plies (45 and

0, in this case) under impact, the plies are clamped remotely and impacted with a blunt indenter (or by forces transmitted through intervening plies), producing damage under the indenter, and in annular zone between the indenter and remote support. Now consider the local forces operating on the plies in two regions labelled A and B, Between the indenter and remote support. The fibers strip of the upper ply just below the indenter separates from the remote clamping due to the downward deflection produced by the impact forces. This is marked as a center strip in Figure 4. At A, there are peel forces acting to promote delamination. Conversely, at B, the ply curvatures and tensions produce a net force acting to keep the plies together, and delamination would not be favored. So the A-A direction forms the major axis of the delamination in the considered interply.

Figure 6 shows the sizes of delamination for two types of laminate, Q1 and Q2, and the facesheets of four types of sandwich plates, Q1H3, Q1H8, Q2H3, and Q2H8 at each interply location under $E_0=3.78$ J. The impact delamination area between layers depends on the interply location in thickness direction and the difference in angular orientation of two plies making up the interply. The interply [-45/-45..] has no delamination because there is no difference in the two adjacent plies. Delaminations between plies whose relative angular orientation, $\alpha=90^\circ$ (45/-45, -45/45, 0/90, 90/0, in Q2 layup) tend to be larger than those between plies where $\alpha=45^\circ$ (in Q1 layup). The relative angular difference between layers in Q1 layup is 45° except the center layers [-45/-45..]. In Q1 layup the damage size is dependent upon the location of the interply from the impact layer. The largest delamination occurs in the farthest interply for Q1 laminates but it shifts inward for Q1H3 and Q1H8 sandwich plates. This is due to the difference in bending deformation. In case of sandwich plate, the bending deformation is restricted due to the support of Nomex core. So the total damage size of the facesheet of a sandwich plate is usually smaller than that of a laminate.

Figure 7 shows the relationship between the absorbed energy, E_s , and the energy absorption per unit delamination area, E_s/A . Energy absorption per unit delamination is almost constant for composite laminates if no fiber damage occurs under low speed impact loading. For Q1 layup, the absorbed energy per unit delamination is 0.42 J/cm² and for Q2 layup, 0.33 J/cm². In other words, Q1 layup is more damage resistant than Q2 layup. Sandwich structures have additional energy absorbing mechanism - core crushing / shear deformation. The facesheets of sandwich plates, Q1H3 and Q1H8, are more damage resistant than Q1 laminate due to the role of honeycomb core. The Q2H8 sandwich plate has higher value of E_s/A than Q2 laminate for higher absorbed energy than 2.1 Joules. But the reverse is true for lower absorbed energy than 2.1 Joules. So it can be concluded that the Q2H8 sandwich plate is more damage resistant than Q2 laminate for higher absorbed energy than 2.1 Joules. In case of Q2H3 sandwich, the transition value of absorbed energy is about 3.1 Joules. For layups of small relative angular orientation between adjacent plies such as Q1, the facesheet of a sandwich plate gets more damage resistant than a laminate of same layup sequence due to the existence of core. But for layups of large relative angular orientation between adjacent plies such as Q2, the facesheet of a sandwich plate is less damage resistant than a laminate of a

layup sequence below a certain value of absorbed energy. Above the transition value of absorbed energy, the facesheet with Q2 layup sequence of a sandwich is tougher than a laminate with the same layup. Generally, the facesheet of a sandwich with higher density core is more damage resistant than that with lower density core.

4. CONCLUSION

1. The shape and size of delamination were measured in each interply location of composite laminates and composite laminated facesheets of sandwich plates by deply technique.
2. The observed shape of impact delamination shows that the major axis of delamination falls upon the fiber direction of the immediate lower ply and a center band is parallel to the fiber direction of the immediate upper ply.
3. Laminates of small relative angular orientation between adjacent plies tend to be more damage resistant than those of large relative angular orientation.
4. For layups of small relative angular orientation between adjacent plies such as Q1, the facesheet of a sandwich plate gets more damage resistant than a laminate of same layup sequence due to the existence of core. But for layups of large relative angular orientation between adjacent plies such as Q2, the facesheet of a sandwich plate is less damage resistant than a laminate of a layup sequence below a certain value of absorbed energy.
5. Generally, the facesheet of a sandwich with higher density core is more damage resistant than that with lower density core.

REFERENCES

1. N. Takeda, et. al., J. Comp. Mat., 15, 157-174, (1981).
2. R. T. Potter, Proc Int Conf Post Failure Analysis Techniques for Fiber Reinforced Composites, Dayton, Ohio, USA (1985).
3. G. Clark, Composites, 20 (3), 209-214, (May 1989).
4. Seongho Hong and Dashin Liu, Experimental Mechanics, 29(2), 115-120, (June 1989).
5. J. M. Slepetz, et. al., Engineering Fracture Mechanics, 8, 758 (1976).
6. W. G. J. 't Hart, " The Effect of Impact Damage on the Tension-Compression Fatigue Properties of Sandwich Panels with Face Sheets of Carbon/Epoxy," National Aerospace Laboratory, Amsterdam (Netherlands) (Dec. 1981).
7. M. L. Bernard and P. A. Lagace, J. of Reinforced Plates and Composites, 8, 432-445, (Sep. 1989).
8. W. K. Shih and B. Z. Jang, Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites, 8, 270, (May 1989).

Figure 1. Depleting Specimen

Figure 2. Load History Curves for $E_0=3.78\text{ J}$

Figure 3. Energy History Curves for $E_0=3.78\text{ J}$

Figure 4. Shape and Size of Delamination in Each Interply Locations of Laminate and Facesheet of Sandwich plate with Layup Sequence, [0/45/90/-45].

Figure 5. Delamination Model[3]

Figure 6. Ply by Ply Delamination Distribution for $E_o=3.78$ J

Figure 7. Absorbed Energy per Unit Delamination Area for Various Specimens